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ABSTRACT BOOK

**HEALTH MANAGEMENT:
MANAGING THE PRESENT
AND SHAPING THE FUTURE**

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Climate Pact Ambassador role in the decarbonisation of healthcare sector

Authors: Prof Dr Marija Jevtic^{1,2,3}, Dr Vlatka Matkovic⁴, Prof Catherine Bouland³

¹Faculty of Medicine University of Novi Sad, Serbia. ²Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Serbia. ³Research collaborator at the Université Libre de Bruxelles, Research Centre on Environmental and Occupational Health, School of Public Health, Belgium. ⁴Health & Environment Alliance (HEAL), Belgium

Climate change requires swift action aimed at adaptation and mitigation. Health sector is witnessing increased healthcare needs due to climate change and emerging diseases. Globally, the health sector is emitting 5% of total greenhouse gases (GHG). It is necessary, thus, to make a strategic decision for the decarbonisation process of this sector. To become an environmentally-friendly and sustainable healthcare system requires a broad and fundamental transformation. The COVID-19 pandemic crisis has been a significant disruption to all health systems but confirms the need to transform them into zero pollution systems.

The objective of the EU Green Deal and European Climate Pact is to encourage actions aimed at climate neutrality. The role of the European Climate Pact Ambassador is, among other things, to motivate and contribute to the understanding of the need for actions aimed at mitigation and adaptation to climate change. Encouraging the health sector for climate-friendly actions designed to reduce GHG is of great importance, as well as all strategic decisions in that direction.

Health sector should focus on: energy efficiency of their buildings, different work processes, low-carbon transport vehicles, but also initiatives for the green environment. Medical waste management, including recycling of single-use personal protective equipment and other waste, is a big challenge during the COVID-19 pandemic with a possibility for large achievements in reducing pollution and saving on embedded carbon in disposable matters. Healthcare sector contribution to air pollution, land and water pollution also needs to be considered. Digital health innovations should be considered as a potential in providing health care which is reducing GHG emissions. It is also important to underline that the health-care sector has a significant role in improving intakes of healthy, sustainable food and teaching in healthy dietary choices.

European Academies' Science Advisory Council (EASAC) and Federation of European Academies of Medicine (FEAM) produced an important document for healthcare professionals regarding the decarbonisation of the Health Sector. In this Commentary it is underlined that policy-makers and health sector managers should work together in developing climate change mitigation and adaptation actions.

Necessary action could be strengthened by Climate Pact Ambassadors aiming to ensure that the health sector itself achieves ambitious decarbonisation targets and systems change in the health-care sector which requires that healthcare organisations at all levels adopt sustainability organisational culture. Beside the primary task of the healthcare sector – healing patients and improving their health, healthcare professionals should be aware of their responsibility in potential externalities due to GHG emissions, (as a population health consequence). Health sector should emphasise also the importance of decarbonisation in the education process, through the formal education, as well as lifelong learning.